

**ANALYSIS OF “IT IS HARD TO BE HUMAN”
(ODAM BO‘LISH QIYIN)**

Ne‘matjonova Gulyora,

Djabbarova Nilufar

Samarkand State University of Kattakurgan branch

Research advisor: **Murodova Mukaddas**

ABSTRACT

“It is hard to be human” (Odam bo‘lish qiyin) - Written by the People’s Writer of Uzbekistan Olmas Umarbekov. In this work there is a true breath of life. The work is the writer’s first novel, written in 1969. The simplicity of the language and the vividness of the events are noteworthy. Olmas Umarbekov has a special role in the development of Uzbek prose in the second half of the last century. His novel "It’s Hard to Be a human" is one of the most widely read works written about youth life, spiritual and moral problems, complex human relationships. The main idea of the work is to explain to the reader concepts such as the fact that not everyone can preserve their loyalty to such a great feeling as love, not to be deceived by the deceitful feelings of the world, and most importantly, never to bow to the ego.

Keywords: Olmas Umarbekov, It is hard to be human, love, justice, scientist.

“It’s hard to be human.” First of all, let’s analyze the title of the work. The choice of the title of the work shows how skillful and eloquent the writer is. The work is aptly named. “It’s hard to be human” can appeal to every reader. Because everyone is trying to save the name of humanity in this world. It’s hard to be human. It is so difficult that only the character of Abdulla in the play proved it. Wasn’t he a kind, kind-hearted, compassionate person who tried to resist when his uncle Obid killed a quail he had

attracted with his charming voice. What made him so selfish? Maybe it's interest, maybe it's Professor Tursun's desire to take him to Leningrad. Maybe it is. The work shows the selfish and selfish image of a person who has been brought up for years, even his relatives did not notice it. After reading the work, I thought: does a person have a lot of heart? Is it possible for a person to hate the person he loves? Why did Abdulla look at Gulchehra's letters with disdain and disdain. He didn't even write the answer. He loved the Planet with the hope that it would secure my future. Maybe he didn't love. He put his self-interested love above the sincere love of a girl. He destroyed his first love with his feet. He could have looked at the love of his father Gofurjon and his mother Shahodat. But he didn't care. In their house there was a devoted love for each other, even if they didn't have a lot of money. That's what they say, one mother gives birth to an alvan child. Yes, I am sure.

I also really liked the narration in the play. In it, a Muslim king has a pharaoh as his father, and no matter how much he is warned, he will not give it up. One day he will become pharaoh and kill his father, but according to the prophecy he will spend the rest of his life without meaning. There is also a song sample in the work. Every character in the play fulfilled its unique role: grandmother Hojar, brother Gofurjon, brother Sayyora, brother Obid, brother Tursin, mother Shahodat and others. It is difficult to be a person." in my opinion, in these images, gofurjon brother melts each sound of this sentence with features such as humanity, kindness, forgiveness, and kindness. But these feelings are not present in his son Abdullah. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to say that this sentence was the main title of his life. He is portrayed as a man who lost his sense of humanity in pursuit of becoming a scientist. I had a hard time reading the end of the work. The turn of events brought tears to my eyes. My voice was hoarse.

If we analyze the work from a literary point of view, the first knot in the work begins with two young people accidentally seeing each other after many years. In the play, several events can be exemplified by several nodes. For example, the obstacle of Abdulla's feelings about Gulchehra is a knot in his inner world. Or the unexpected

appearance of Sayyora and her father in the lives of Gulchehra and Abdulla is one of the knots in the play.

There are many conflicts in the play. For example, in the inner and outer worlds of Gulchehra, the contradiction between going to the city or staying in the village, or Abdullah's conflict between Sayyora and prestige, or sincere feelings towards Gulchehra, creates a conflict. The conflict between man and nature is reflected in Abdullah's position on the train. It is as if Abdulla is happy: he flies in the seventh heaven, and he is silent and fearful, as if nature is warning him of endless troubles.

The culmination of the play is Gulchehra's death... And behind it, Abdullah's torment of conscience... He blames himself and his fleeting desires for this death.

In the play, the solution emerges in the process of Abdullah telling the story of how much he loves two couples while sitting on the train track, that is, Abdullah says; "Cherish the person you love as much as possible, never hurt them. Even the thing that makes you happy in the world is not worth an iota in front of his smile"

Form and content, plot elements, epilogue, conflict, solution etc. are represented in the composition.

At the very beginning of the work, there is a sample of folklore, that is, the work begins with a narration. In addition, there are various proverbs and wise words.

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